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SUSTAINING STUDENT MOTIVATION THROUGH SELF-DIRECTED ENGAGEMENT IN SCIENCE COMMUNICATION PROJECTS - A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Technische Universität Berlin has launched two courses with an innovative concept for science communication: *lab:present* (since 2017) and *lab:prepare* (since 2019) encourage and empower students to present scientific topics in public.

lab:present fosters and rewards the commitment of highly motivated students who work on projects that are intended for public display. The sister-course *lab:prepare* provides hands-on knowledge and skills on how to take research findings out of the lab and into non-scientific contexts.

Both courses are open to students of all faculties. The curriculum includes project management, working in interdisciplinary teams, basics of making (3D design, 3D print, electronics, microcontrollers etc.), and science communication theory. In the course, students develop projects of their choice with the goal of presenting scientific topics in an accessible way.

Although presenting in the public was almost impossible in 2020 due to the pandemic, the *lab:prepare* course continued. From April 2020, we offered the course primarily online and found that interest and motivation for the course did not decrease. The quality of the projects, the dropout rate, and the time commitment of the students remained at a high level.

We claim that self-directed work in interdisciplinary teams on projects that extend beyond the university has a great impact on student engagement, which is a major issue in online teaching. We report on our teaching concepts, the general structure of the course and compare the online implementation with the pre-pandemic version of *lab:prepare*.

1 INTRODUCTION

Before the courses *lab:prepare* and *lab:present* started at *Technische Universität Berlin*, supervisors of other courses like *Projektlabor Physik*² encouraged students to present their experiments in public. This led to some remarkable results and was the motivation to establish a separate course on presenting science in public - *lab:present* - and later the associated preparatory course *lab:prepare* (starting winter term 2019).

The courses *lab:prepare* and *lab:present* are open to students of all disciplines. The courses are modular and can be taken independently of each other. In order to complete the *lab:present* module, students have to present a topic of their choice in the public. For example, students informed about artificial intelligence at a convention or organized an event on the applications of mathematics in various professional fields.

We also found that many students were particularly motivated to present hardware installations, such as physics experiments where knowledge of microcontrollers and new manufacturing techniques like 3D printing are crucial.

lab:prepare was founded to support students in their science communication projects and encourage them to work in interdisciplinary teams. In order to successfully communicate topics from their studies, they first develop concepts to make these complex topics accessible to a broader audience. They are free to choose the media and format they use: e.g. installations, videos, podcasts or simulations. In the first semester *lab:prepare* was offered entirely in presence. In spring 2020, at the start of the pandemic, we switched to an online format. As the *lab:present* course could hardly be continued during the Corona crisis, the focus of this paper is on the *lab:prepare* course.

In the following section, we introduce the two main teaching concepts that drive our courses: student science communication and interdisciplinary project-based learning. In Section 3 we explain how the *lab:prepare* course is structured and describe which aspects of the course facilitate the transition to an online format. In the subsequent Section we report on the motivation of the students in our course. We will conclude with some example projects and suggestions on how our findings can be implemented in other courses.

2 TEACHING CONCEPTS

2.1 Student Science Communication

Although science communication is more and more recognized as a responsibility of scientists, it is still not integrated in curricula or offered as an additional course at most universities. Giving students the opportunity to present scientific topics to the general public has many positive effects, as stated by Brownell et.al. [1].

² <https://www.pl-physik.tu-berlin.de>

In our courses students develop projects in which they present topics of their field in an accessible way. The societal role of students is predestined for communicating science to a broad audience: It is easy for them to empathize with laypersons, because they are still learning the core concepts of the scientific method as well as the terminology of their field.

Preparing a topic for a non-scientific audience deepens students' understanding of their subject and the opportunity to learn science communication early in their careers enhances their ability to express scientific topics intelligibly [2]. We also observe that communicating scientific content in an extramural context promotes identification with the subject and increases students' motivation to engage with their field of study.

Giving students the opportunity to report results of their scientific work enables them to act as representatives of their field. We encourage the students in our courses to enter a bidirectional dialogue with the public. Allowing the audience to voice their priorities and concerns builds trust and increases the probability that the communication is successful [3]. With this we want to get away from the Information Deficit Model in science communication and promote the Contextualist Model.

Another aspect that we address in our courses is internal science communication. Professional exchange between scientists forms a large part of scientific work that students are not aware of until they start their own research. The preparation of their projects creates the necessity to talk about topics of their studies, ideally beyond disciplinary boundaries and across various academic levels.

2.2 Interdisciplinary Project-Based Learning

In our courses, students from all faculties can join. They are free to choose both the topic of their project and their project group. When forming groups, we encourage course participants to work with students from other subjects.

Interdisciplinarity in teaching has great potential to have a lasting impact on students. Interaction with students from other disciplines opens up the “third space” which gives room for critical thinking, helps to develop new knowledge and teaches to be open to different perspectives [4]. The focus of today's education on the development of professional skills should be accompanied by social competences: co-operation, communication and self-competence. This has also a positive effect on the competitiveness in the labour market [5].

Project-Based Learning (PBL) is a student-driven, teacher-facilitated approach to learning. When students are active during the learning process, learning is more effective and their understanding is improved. The use of project-based methods in science and technology has been shown to increase undergraduate students' self-efficacy beliefs beyond those of students taught using traditional methods [6]. PBL also enables them to develop better performance skills.

3 COURSE IMPLEMENTATION OF LAB:PREPARE

3.1 General Course Structure

Students learn the technical and organizational basics for presenting scientific content to the public. This includes, for example, the design and implementation of science-related installations or the generally understandable presentation of complex topics. In the three semesters that the course exists, we had 10 - 20 - 32 participants in WS19/20 - SS20 - WS20/21 respectively, coming mainly from STEM programs, but also with backgrounds of psychology, sociology or media science.

In the following we present the basic building blocks of the *lab:prepare* course. This applies to both offline (pre-covid) and online teaching (during covid).

Table 1. General Course Structure

lecture period				lecture-free period	
1. month	2. month	3. month	4. month	5. month	6. month
survey	weekly workshops in the seminar		survey	submissions	
project pitches	small homework every two weeks			individual meetings on demand	
group formation	work on group projects				

During the lecturing period we meet weekly for two hours. In the beginning of the semester we conduct a survey about the students' backgrounds, interests and possible projects to adjust the curriculum accordingly. We try to promote early group formation and encourage students to pitch their project ideas. After the project groups have formed, we offer a series of workshops and exercises that are adjusted to fit the topics chosen by the students. These workshops include mostly making skills like 3D printing or microcontroller programming, but also theoretical aspects of science communication.

The weekly two hour meetings are usually structured as followed:

- general information (10min)
- content: pitches, workshops, Q&As etc. (15-45 min)
- work on group projects, feedback (open end)

At the end of the semester we conduct another survey, the results of which are presented in part below. Most projects are finalized in the lecture-free period, where we offer meetings on demand. The final submission for the student groups is their project documentation.

3.2 Online Implementation

We began offering our course online in March 2020, when contact restrictions to prevent the spread of Covid-19 went into effect. Since then, organizational and lecture documents are managed via the online portal ISIS (*Information System for Instructors*)

and Students) of the *Technische Universität Berlin* and weekly meetings are held with the hosting service *Zoom Video Communications*.

Instead of weekly scheduled workshops in presence, we offer different asynchronous learning materials for the course including videos on 3D design, 3D print, microcontrollers, video editing and much more. This way we can focus on more interactive formats in the virtual presence sessions: open Q&A's, presentations of students concerning their projects and most importantly time for the project groups in Zoom breakout rooms³. We found the breakout room feature in particular is a great catalyst for good communication and self-organization inside the groups.

We encouraged the students to choose formats that work well online, like videos, podcasts or simulations. Nonetheless, some groups decided to do hardware projects and work mainly with tools they had available at home. We supported these projects by handing out material and printing 3D objects. Students picked up the hardware at the university or we mailed it.

Since the summer term 2020 we also provide our own wiki for documenting the projects and collecting resources⁴. We motivate the students to start the process of documentation early on, to collect valuable information for their final submission. The whole website is open access to promote the visibility of their projects for other student groups as well as the interested public.

Although previously simple things, such as handing out materials or demonstrating hardware applications, were more complicated in the online format, we observed that communication between students, self-management and their motivation did not deteriorate. In the following section, we identify and evaluate key indicators of student motivation to further quantify the latter claim.

4 ASPECTS OF STUDENT MOTIVATION IN LAB:PREPARE

Several studies surveying students that were forced to study online in the last two semesters show that students miss face-to-face interaction with other students [7]. Another issue is the (self-) motivation, in particular when the course lacks any interaction [8, 9].

In this section, we report on the performance of students taking our *lab:prepare* course and how this leads us to believe that our course structure and teaching approaches promote student motivation. In order to evaluate the student motivation, we identified three key indicators: the drop-out rate, quality of the projects and time commitment. We find that these indicators have not changed with the online implementation of *lab:prepare*.

³ sessions that are split off from the main Zoom meeting for each project. The students can freely switch between them and can go to the main meeting to get in contact with the supervisors.

⁴ <https://www.labprepare.tu-berlin.de/wiki/doku.php>

The first indicator is the drop-out rate. As the term progresses students are faced with an increasing workload, especially during the examination period at the end of the terms. As the student's individual motivation is a necessary condition for successful completion of a course, one can conclude that a comparatively low drop-out rate is an indication for a high motivation of the course participants.

In the winter term 19/20, which was held entirely offline, we achieved a drop out rate of less than 20%. Comparing this to our current dropout rate we find that it has not changed significantly with the switch to the full-online format. We rather observe even lower dropout rates, although in online courses dropout rates above 25% are common [10].

The second indicator we use to assess the achievement of students' learning goals is the quality of their projects. Our teaching staff evaluated the group projects in terms of innovation, target group-specific communication, quality of scientific content and their documentation. Despite the difficulties that come with the online format, the quality of group projects remains at a high level.

The last aspect regarding motivation that we want to address is the weekly workload. As the project goals are almost freely chosen by the students, the weekly workload is not oriented at an abstract learning goal but is determined by the ambitions of the students. Our course surveys in the two online semesters show that students spent on average about 3.5h in addition to the two-hour seminar per week. This results in a workload of 80h per lecture period. Adding the time students spend on their projects in the lecture-free period, including the final submission, the total workload of the course ranges from 90-120 hours or more. This exceeds the expected workload for 3 ECTS, which is 75-90 hours. However, according to our survey, the majority of students consider their individual workload to be appropriate. This leads us to believe that the intrinsic motivation of our students to achieve their project goals is very high.

Our evaluation shows that the *lab:prepare* course sustains students motivation in online environments. We assume that our two teaching concepts are the main reason for this success: student science communication and interdisciplinary project-based learning foster student engagement.

5 EXAMPLE PROJECTS

In the following we want to showcase two projects that meet the course requirements in an outstanding way. The first is the Helmholtz' Siren Bike, which demonstrates physical properties of sound and its production (offline semester, winter term 19/20). The second example deals with the social issue of period poverty (online semester, winter term 20/21). Both projects are interdisciplinary in that the Helmholtz' Siren Bike combines a physics experiment with a musical and artistic approach while the Period Poverty project addresses a topic from the social sciences using technology.

5.1 Helmholtz' Siren Bike⁵

This project aims to educate the spectator about the production of sound waves by combining an old approach with a new interactive method. In this installation (see Figure 3), sound is produced by means of a rotating perforated plate.

Holes are lasered into a plate in concentric circles. If a nozzle is now placed at these circles of holes so that air can flow through the holes, the pitch of the sound is determined by the speed of rotation of the plate, as well as the number of holes on one circle. This arrangement was developed by Hermann von Helmholtz and was a popular method in the 19th century for producing sound waves in a controlled manner and for studying their properties.

To introduce a performative aspect to the set-up, the plate is mounted on a jacked-up bicycle instead of a rear wheel. The performer can then control the speed of the perforated plate and regulate the volume of various sounds that can be produced with the plate via valves. The bicycle can be played like an instrument. It thus enables visitors to explore sound waves in a playful way.

Fig. 3. The playable Siren Bike at an exhibition of Akademie der Künste Berlin

⁵ https://www.labprepare.tu-berlin.de/wiki/doku.php?id=helmholtz_sches_sirenenfahrrad

5.2 Period Poverty⁶

This project aims to raise awareness about period poverty and the stigma associated with period blood. Period products are expensive and therefore not accessible to people with low incomes. These people then have to resort to other means and this can have devastating, even fatal, consequences.

Through education about toxic shock syndrome and related topics, the student group advocates for free access to period products. The project also contributes to the de-stigmatising of menstruation through art: the group designed an exhibition featuring an ever-bleeding 3D printed vulva (see Figure 4) and several sustainable alternative period products like period cup, period pants, period sponge, reusable / washable pad.

Due to the pandemic it was not possible to realize the exhibition during the semester. However, it should not be neglected how much education on the subject has already taken place within the course through presentations to the group. The technical setup and the 3D design for the ever-bleeding vulva were carefully planned and discussed with the teaching staff during the online sessions. The 3D print was made at the university and handed over to the students along with the other technical parts.

Fig. 4. 3D printed sculpture addressing the social issue of period poverty.

⁶ <https://www.labprepare.tu-berlin.de/wiki/doku.php?id=ws2021:periodenprodukte>

6 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In this paper we presented the two courses *lab:present* and *lab:prepare* at the *Technische Universität Berlin*, which are based on the teaching concepts of student science communication and interdisciplinary project based learning. We focused on the online implementation of the course *lab:prepare* and compared the motivation of students in the online format with the previous offline format. Our observations show consistently high student motivation in both online and offline implementation, although student motivation is a major issue in online semesters due to covid-19.

For our courses blended learning formats may thus be ideal for post-corona teaching, keeping the advantages of online formats such as break-out rooms, open access project documentation platforms and asynchronous learning materials.

We also believe that project-based learning has great potential for online formats in general, since it ensures a certain amount of interaction between the students. Although we cannot provide empiric data about the effects of science communicative aspects on student motivation, we assume that preparing a topic for the general public also increases the students' motivation. Based on our experiences we suggest to implement both project-based learning as well as science communication aspects in other university courses including basic lectures. The student groups in our courses mainly work on their own, so the additional support from supervisors should be manageable. This could lead to a higher identification of the students with their subject, deeper understanding of the topics as well as lower drop-out rates.

We see the need to connect science and the public from several directions. More and more funding opportunities, such as calls from institutions like *Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung*, include outreach. Therefore the next generation of scientists must be trained in external science communication. A study by C. Könneker et al. surveying young scientists shows that they are open to engaging in dialogue with the public, but also that science communication training at universities is still poor [11].

We believe that science communication courses at universities have great potential. The societal need for a dialogue between the public and the scientific community as well as the variety of skills students acquire in implementing the projects, demonstrates the many levels on which our course concept can be meaningful.

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